

TAKING KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT TO LOGICAL CONCLUSION

* Dr. Maya Mainkar

* Assistant Professor

Affiliated to University of Pune, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Abstract

Knowledge Management (KM) gained importance in 1990. Its purpose was to holistically organise the information of an organisation. Davenport said that KM was about capturing, distributing, and effectively using knowledge. Gartner Group wanted an integrated approach of identifying, capturing, evaluating, retrieving, and sharing of all the enterprise's information assets. In an attempt to achieve this, knowledge was categorized as explicit, implicit, and tacit, where difference was made between collecting and connecting information and between information that is available and that which exists within the mind of a human being. Knowledge is captured in organisations through Lesson Learned Database, Expertise Location, and Communities of Practices (CoPs).

Knowledge Management was initially driven by Information Technology. This creation of knowledge was soon coupled with knowledge sharing and finally to the stage of Taxonomy and Content Management. The last was based on the rationality that knowledge is of no use if it cannot be found. Knowledge Management is still at a primitive stage. It will improve if managers and workers are trained to be creative. This means they should constantly use their imagination to bring forth good ideas. Human beings have to be trained in creativity. The earlier this begins the better. The process should ideally begin at school. This creativity teaches human beings to establish objectives, choose knowledge appropriate to it and then find ways to use it. This is wisdom. Organisations must inspire wisdom if they want to improve bottom lines or prevent bankruptcy.

Key words: *Knowledge Management, Communities of Practices (CoPs), explicit, implicit, tacit,*

*Corresponding author: *Dr. Maya Mainkar

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INTRODUCTION

Knowledge Management (KM) as a concept first gained importance in 1990. Its purpose was to organize the information of an organisation in a holistic manner.¹This changed when Davenport said that “Knowledge Management is the process of capturing, distributing and effectively using knowledge.”²

These are two different definitions of Knowledge Management. The focus of the first definition is on knowledge in an organisation. The second adds distribution and use of knowledge.

In sharp contrast to the simple, stark, and to the point definition of Knowledge Management by Davenport, the definition most frequently used is the one created by the Gartner Group (Duhon 1998).³

It states “Knowledge Management is a discipline that promotes an integrated approach of identifying, capturing, evaluating, retrieving, and sharing of all the enterprise’s information assets. These assets may include databases, documents, policies, procedures, and previously un-captured expertise and experience in individual workers.”

Definition of Gartner Group

The Gartner Group lays stress on a few things. It stresses on an integrated approach of identifying, evaluating, retrieving, and sharing of information.

Integration involves people working in groups. Thus the definition lays stress on people working with a similarity of purpose while managing knowledge. This group has to recognize information which is worthy to the purpose of the organisation and to the objectives that the group has set out to achieve. This requires the ability of the group to establish the value of knowledge available to them.

Types of Knowledge Management

In the literature of Knowledge Management, knowledge is commonly categorized as either explicit or tacit. Tacit information is that which lies in people’s heads.

The above characterisation is too simplistic. It is also misleading. What lies in people’s head may be a range of unsubstantiated sensations, which need evaluation before they can be considered worthy of acceptance. A better, though not completely acceptable, characterisation describes knowledge as explicit, implicit and tacit. The three are defined as follows.

- (a) Explicit information or knowledge is set out in tangible form, which means it is definite and provable.
- (b) Implicit information or knowledge is not set out in tangible form but could be made explicit.
- (c) Tacit information or knowledge is inside a person, who has extreme difficulty in operationally setting it out in tangible form.

Even this categorization is not very easy to understand, especially in regards to the information in tangible form and the one that exists within the mind of a human being. This over-simplification between collecting and connecting knowledge overlooks many vital points.

Knowledge and Information

There is also a problem in considering knowledge and information as separate things. Knowledge is information and skills gained through experience or education. It is the sum of what is known.⁴ Information is facts or knowledge provided or learned.⁵ There is in fact, very little difference between the two words. This must be born in mind while managing knowledge.

The Role of Knowledge Management

Knowledge Management (KM) has a very crucial role. It is to make the data of an organisation available to its members through portals and with the use of content management systems. There is another obvious role of Knowledge Management. It is called Content Management. It is also known as Enterprise Content Management.

Knowledge Management also provides a few others things apart from content management. These are Lesson Learned Databases, Expertise Location, and Communities of Practices (CoPs).

Lesson Learned Databases

This is an attempt to capture knowledge that has been operationally obtained but would not have been captured in a fixed medium. Its main emphasis is to capture the knowledge that exists inside a person and then make it explicit, so that it is clear and detailed, with no room for confusion.

The above requires the ability to clearly establish the information available inside a person's mind. It also requires that this information is available for us from other people in a manner that there is no confusion or ambiguity in what we have received.

This database is not new. Many organisations do it. One fine example is the debriefing provided by pilots after a flying mission. This happened eighty years ago, when pilots of the Second World War provided information and shared their experiences after they returned to base from a mission. This debriefing provided military intelligence and also lessons learned during the mission. (McInerney and Koeing. 2011).⁶

What happens in the world of flying also happens in the corporate world. There are plenty of debriefs in meetings during or after an important activity.

This debriefing, however does not always provide true lessons. It fails to provide true lessons due to many reasons. The most obvious is when the project team is disbanded and its members are sent to other roles without a debriefing (Larry Prusak 2004)⁷ of an after-action report (AAR).

Expertise Location

Expertise Location is an attempt to locate the experts who have the knowledge an organisation needs. These were earlier called “Yellow Page” systems. These experts are located from the information provided in resumes. These give information regarding areas of expertise provided by the employee

in his resume while joining the organisation. In addition to a resume, there are other ways of locating expertise. It includes finding out the training that has been provided to an employee by an organisation as well as his areas of interest.

Communities of Practices (CoPs)

Communities of Practices (CoPs) are groups of individuals with shared interests who discuss problems, best practices, and lessons learned among themselves. (Wenger 1998; Wenger and Snyder 1999)⁸. Most of these CoPs are electronically linked communities, though there are other ways of linking people into communities.

CoPs are not easy to maintain (Durham 2004)⁹. They require a manager, a moderator, and a thought leader. This is not an easy task, even when the three can be done by one person. He has to manage problems, moderate the information to solve the problems, and apply thought to achieve the best possible solutions to the problems under consideration.

Development of Knowledge Management

KM was initially driven by Information Technology. It derived intellectual capital out of the internet. It shared this knowledge

across the organisation to get the better of competition.

The term Knowledge Management was first used in its new context at Mckinsey. Ernst and Young organized the first conference of Knowledge Management in 1992 in Boston (Prusak, 1999)¹⁰ on how to apply new technology to make information and knowledge more effective.

The second stage of Knowledge Management came when it became obvious that using new technology was not enough to enable sharing of information. This meant changes had to be introduced in the corporate culture. This required sharing of information and knowledge. Thus knowledge creation was coupled with knowledge sharing (Nonaka Ikujiro Takeuchi Hirotaka. 1995)¹¹. This brought the concept of communities in practice and created Human Resource Development.

Taxonomy and Content Management

The third stage of Knowledge Management was Taxonomy and Content Management. Taxonomy is the branch of science concerned with classification. It is thus a system of classifying things, which means arranging information or things in an organized manner.

The stage of Taxonomy and Content Management developed from the awareness of the importance of content and its retrievability. This required arrangement, description, and structure of content. The rationale behind this stage is that "it is no use if we try to use it but can't find it."

Others Issues on Knowledge Management

In modern times, people retire early in life. This means information is lost with them. The best way to retain information is to keep the retiree involved and a part of the CoPs. This retains not only his information but also the solutions arrived by him in discussions.

Organisations are now also acquiring knowledge of vendors, suppliers, customers, scholars, and scientists, in addition to the knowledge of the employees. These feedbacks are vital for the growth of an organisation. They improve sales, quality, and a number of other important things.

Managing Knowledge

All that has been said and written about Knowledge Management has brought us this far. It is a step in the right direction. However, we need to move ahead. Those who use old ideas, no matter how good, are left behind by creative competitors. We have

to think of ways to supplement inadequate knowledge.¹² God does not need to think because he has all the knowledge he needs. We have not advanced as per our aspirations because of a god-like attitude in education and in management about teaching and training. We pile on knowledge and statistics. It is wrongly believed that sufficient data creates an idea. So funds are poured into data-mongering without a thought for ideas that used to provoke science in old days. We have to always keep in mind that knowledge cannot substitute thinking. Nor can thinking substitute knowledge.

We need thinking because we have insufficient knowledge. Teaching knowledge does not generate adequate thinking because knowledge has its own momentum. It greatly reduces our ability to think in a manner that it has the ability to generate good ideas. This is why we often mistake fluency of argument for thinking skill. Fluency and coherent expression are tools of thinking, not thinking itself. Error-free thinking is not necessarily good thinking. We can make a judgement and then use reason to justify it. The best example of this is the existence of God. Human beings provide a mountain of reason for what is primarily beyond reason. We

have to be wary of people who rationalize things after reaching random decisions. Their argument may be flawless, yet the thinking may be terrible because it is based on an error of perception. We also confuse debating skills with thinking: "I can prove you wrong, therefore I am right."

This problem of faulty perception extends in very harmful ways to education. Education prides in scholarship, not understanding that contemplative thinking is not the same as generative thinking. Contemplation is just thinking deeply and at length.¹³ Contemplative thinking is passive, no matter how subtle or acute it may be. Generative thinking establishes what is required and then provides solutions on how it can be acquired. It deals with the world and takes action, even if the knowledge is incomplete.¹⁴

Thinking and Information

Information can be good or bad, useless or useful, helpful or harmful. Its relevance is decided by our objectives. Arriving at objectives requires precise thinking based on what we want. It is also required to search the precise information that is required for it and finally to use this information to act till we achieve our objectives. The key word while trying to find out what we want and

how we can achieve what we want is creativity. We succeed when we are surrounded by good ideas.

Creativity and Thinking

Thinking is of little consequence if it is not creative, where imagination is used to arrive at good ideas. We can progress only when we constantly replace ordinary ideas with good ideas or good ideas with better ones.

There is one problem in creativity. We have to be trained to be creative; otherwise we keep on generating thoughts, without knowing if they are good and useful for us. Random thinking leads to confusion. This, in turn, leads to bad conclusions.

Teaching Creativity

We have a series of chaotic sensations when we are born. These do not become creative thinking because we are not born creative. We have to be trained to be creative. This training has to begin early and needs a technique which can generate it. We have to start in school, say from class V. Earlier than that is an unresolved area of creative thought. Later than that means we delay to create a vital human quality.

In order to train students to be creative, teachers and trainers will have to stop

"pumping in" the contents of textbooks in front of baffled students. It generates nothing and concentration is very low. Moreover, mindless listening may result in random thinking but it does not generate creativity.

It is now generally accepted that creativity is achieved in education when there is purposeful reading, speaking, thinking, writing and listening. At present none of these are available in the classroom. It can be achieved if students read and discuss small portions of a textbook, present the portion to other groups and then answer questions asked by other groups.¹⁵ This training in creativity has to begin early and continue in Knowledge Management. Using imagination to bring forth good ideas is a habit. Once formed, it can create excellence for ever.

The above technique of teaching and training is a combination of discussions, brainstorming, elocution, communication, analyzing and presentation skills, and group dynamism. Out of these, group dynamism is of vital importance. It is similar to the Master Mind Club that Napoleon Hill advanced.¹⁶

The teaching technique begins early because it helps in accumulating, absorbing and

utilizing vast amounts of knowledge and skills. Organisations are unhappy at the quality of management students they receive. This complaint can reduce considerably, if students acquire good communication and analyzing skills as well as the ability to think creatively.

Group Dynamism

Group dynamism is the highest form of group discussion. It happens when two or more people discuss to achieve a common cause, path and destination. When this happens there is an explosion of energy which is many times more than the number of brains involved. This is also the principle of the “Master Mind”.¹⁷

Benefits to Organisations

Organisations cannot prosper without people who have the power to buy things. With up to 80 per cent of India below the poverty line, depending on who is saying what, the ability of Indians to buy is very poor. The best Corporate Social Responsibility that business houses can have is to upgrade the way students think. The technique explained earlier requires no money and is many times more beneficial than building schools.

At present 414 million Indians are below the poverty line, if we think it is sufficient to

earn seventy-five rupees per day. The number becomes more than 800 million if the amount is increased to one hundred and fifty rupees per day.

Human beings are not meant to fail. They fail only because they are not taught to think creatively. Organisations must understand that Knowledge Management has to expand its boundaries if it is to lift dipping bottom lines or businesses from going bankrupt.

Wisdom and Intelligence

Knowledge is a range of information. Wisdom is the ability to have or show experience, knowledge, and good judgement.¹⁸ Intelligence is the ability to gain and apply knowledge and skills.¹⁹ This makes it obvious that knowledge is of limited consequence unless we know how to use it in order to achieve objectives. This is why intelligence development should be as much a criteria for corporate excellence as managing knowledge.

The Future of Knowledge Management

Many analysts believe that Knowledge Management is here to stay. They quote the number of articles that exist on it in business literature. These have risen from zero in 1993 to nearly 1100 in 2013. In addition, the words Knowledge Management or KM were

used about 7500 times in articles in 2001. It rose to 1, 20,100 in the year 2011.

This is good news. However, just rise in awareness of an idea or concept is not enough. We must know that the true significance of each word, idea, or concept has to be understood in a wise and intelligent manner. We also have to find the definitions of words, something which even the best among us do not do. A large amount of inefficiency, prejudice, and corporate failure will vanish if definitions of words are clearly understood. It is now well established that the "truth or falsehood of all of man's conclusion, inferences, thought and knowledge rests on the truth or falsehood of his definitions."²⁰ Knowledge Management thus, will improve bottom lines and prevent businesses from going bankrupt if they add creativity, intelligence and wisdom to it. This is easy. All business houses need to do is to empower human beings by opening their minds to the wonderful possibility of creative excellence.

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